

Corrosion Behaviour of Lead in Chloroacetic Acid Solutions

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The corrosion behaviour of lead in aqueous solutions of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids at different concentrations has been investigated. The maximum steady state potentials are achieved from the diagrams of potential-time measurements. The shift of steady state potential towards more negative values with increasing acid concentration is probably due to less formation of insoluble corrosion products which adhere to the metal surface. The obtained potential values are found to be related to the concentration of the acid solution by the equation $E = a - b \log c$. The corrosion rate dw/dt per unit projected area of specimen, increases with the concentration of bulk solution. It is suggested that the corrosion of lead in the three acids is anodically controlled. The values of critical current density for passivation are found to depend on the acid concentration in solution and on the nature of the anion studied.

EARLIER work has adequately demonstrated that protective coatings are formed on lead in acetic acid solutions¹. The corrosion of Pb in fatty acids can proceed only according to the reactions²

The existence of monovalent lead ions in aqueous solutions was first reported by Denham and Allmand³. In a later study⁴ of the anodic dissolution of lead it was suggested that in some solutions, lead dissolved as monovalent ions and the dissolution to be occurring by two simultaneous processes.

The present work deals with the corrosion behaviour of lead in stagnant solutions of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid. Steady state potentials have been studied as a function of both time and acid concentration. The corrosion rate of lead metal has been further determined using the weight-loss procedure.

Experimental

The lead electrodes used were made from electrolytic lead sticks (BDH) in the form of short rods (0.9 cm dia. \times 2.2 cm) fixed to pyrex glass tubes by araldite. Electrical contacts were achieved through thick copper wires soldered to one end of the rods. The electrodes were abraded successively with 1.0 and 0.0 grades emery papers and then degreased with acetone. The electrode vessel (60 ml) was made of pyrex glass without any rubber connections. The potential of lead electrodes was measured in solutions of AR grade mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids (10^{-3} - $5 \times 10^{-1} M$). Potentials were measured, against SCE using a Pye potentiometer in conjunction with Scalamp galvanometer type MSZ-808. Steady state potentials were considered as when the potential did not alter by

more than 1 mV/5 min. Each experiment was carried out with a newly polished electrode and with a fresh portion of the solution at 24-26°.

Weight-loss experiments were carried out using lead specimens (5 cm \times 2 cm \times 1 mm). These were abraded, degreased, washed, dried and weighed, followed by immersion in 100 ml the test solution at the required temperature. The type and extent of attack were determined at different time periods and at the end of the test period. The samples were then cleaned by water, dried and finally weighed. Solution loss by evaporation was compensated by the addition of double-distilled water. The dissolved lead ions were determined volumetrically using reported method⁵.

The study of critical current density of passivation ($I_{crit.}$) and its dependence on acid concentration was carried out using galvanostatic procedure⁶.

Results and Discussion

Potential-time measurements: Potential-time curves for lead electrodes in stagnant solutions of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids, under open circuit conditions, show that the steady state potential values are shifted towards the negative direction with increasing concentrations, 10^{-3} to $5 \times 10^{-1} M$. This behaviour is similar to that cited for cadmium electrodes in aqueous solutions of mono-, and tri-chloroacetic acids⁷ and the corrosion properties of the aggressive ions^{8,9}. However, it is found¹⁰ that the maximum steady state potentials are achieved from positive direction, in case of copper electrodes in similar acid solutions.

Results of the effect of the molar concentration (c) of the three acids on the values of steady state potential of lead electrodes (Fig. 1), show that the straight line portions of these curves obey a relationship of type (1).

$$E = a - b \log c \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. E. mv. vs log for lead in mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions.

where *a* and *b* are constants depending on the nature of electrolyte, and surface preparation^{9,11}. The values of *b* range from 5 to 8 mV in concentration 5×10^{-1} - 10^{-3} M and approximately equal to 30 mV in more dilute solutions. For one and the same acid the potential becomes more negative as the acid concentration increases (Fig. 1).

The shift of the steady state potential values of lead electrode towards less negative values proceeds according to the order, mono- > di- > tri-chloroacetic acid. This behaviour may be explained on the basis of the probable formation of insoluble corrosion products which adhere to the metal surface.

Weight-loss experiments : Results of immersion tests for 5 h in 10^{-3} - 5×10^{-1} M acid solutions showed that the weight loss increases linearly with time. The corrosion rates, computed from the linear plots of weight-loss vs time are presented in Table I.

TABLE I—VARIATION OF CORROSION RATE WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF CHLOROACETIC ACID SOLUTIONS			
Acid concn. M	Corrosion rate, mg/cm ² /h		
	Mono-	Di-	Tri-
5×10^{-1}	0.20	3.75	4.00
10^{-1}	0.14	1.90	3.40
5×10^{-2}	0.12	0.35	2.60
10^{-2}	0.10	0.30	0.40
10^{-3}	0.05	0.05	0.07

The corrosion rate was found to be related to the molar concentration of the acid by equation (2).

$$dw/dt = Kc^n \quad (2)$$

where, *c* is the molar concentration and *K* and *n* are constants depending on the surface preparation of the metal and type of solution⁹.

Plots of log corrosion rate vs log molar concentration of the acid solutions give straight lines with slopes ranging between 0.3-0.8 mg/cm²/h (Fig. 2). The positive slopes indicate that the rate of corrosion of lead increases with the acid concentration. The increase in corrosion rate on going from mono-, di-, to tri-chloroacetic acid solutions is attributed to the increase of aggressiveness of these acids. The increase in corrosion rate, as well as the negative shift in the steady state potential values, with increasing acid concentration, may lead to the suggestion that the corrosion process is determined by depolarization of the anodic controlling reaction, i.e. the corrosion process is anodically controlled¹²⁻¹⁴.

Fig. 2. Relation between corrosion rate of lead and concentration of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions.

Further insight into the role of anions (mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetate) in relation to the corrosion behaviour of lead in stagnant solutions could be gained from the dependence of the critical current densities for passivation (*I* crit.) on concentration. (*I* crit.) was taken as a measure of the effectiveness of electrolyte used as inhibitor or corrosive¹⁵. Thus when lead is anodically polarized in different solutions, the magnitude of (*I* crit.) indicates the activation or passivation characters of the anions. Results given in Fig. 3 for the relationship between log *c* and log (*I* crit.), show that the latter can be expressed by the following form (3).

$$\log (I \text{ crit.}) = a' + b' \log (c) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. Relation between current density and concentration of mono-, di, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions

where the constant a' depends on the anionic nature and the value of $b' = 0.6, 0.9$ and 1.02 for the three

acids, respectively. The values of the critical current density proceed according to the following order :

Mono- < Di- < Tri-chloroacetic acid.

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